

Iodide mediated oxidation of arsenic(III) by cerium(IV) in aqueous sulphuric acid and sulphate media – A kinetic and mechanistic study

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Abstract : A minute (10^{-8} mol dm⁻³) quantity of iodide mediated oxidation of arsenic(III) by cerium(IV) in an aqueous sulphuric acid and sulphate media has been studied spectrophotometrically at 25 °C. The stoichiometry is 1 : 2, i.e. one mole of arsenic(III) requires two moles of cerium(IV). The reaction is first order each in cerium(IV) and iodide concentrations. The order with respect to arsenic(III) is less than unity. Increase in sulphuric acid concentration increased the rate. *In situ* H⁺ ion concentration is calculated by the knowledge of equilibrium constants and the order with respect to H⁺ ion concentration is found to be less than unity. The ionic strength did not have any significant effect on the rate of reaction, whereas rate constant increased with decreasing dielectric constant of the medium. Added products cerium(III) and arsenic(V) did not have any significant effect on the reaction rate. The active species of oxidant and reductant are Ce(SO₄)₂²⁺ and AsI₂⁺ respectively. A suitable mechanism is proposed. The catalytic constant and activation parameters are determined. The results obtained in the present study are similar to that of bromide, chloride and iodide mediated oxidation of antimony(III) by cerium(IV) in aqueous sulphuric acid-sulfate media and are compared and discussed.

Keywords : Kinetics, oxidation, mechanism, arsenic(III), cerium(IV).

Introduction

The stable oxidation states of arsenic are arsenic(III) and arsenic(V). Arsenic compounds commonly occur in insecticides, fungicides and herbicides. Recent trials have shown that arsenic trioxide in low dose can also be a life saver for leukemia patients. The reduction potential¹ of the As^V/As^{III} couple in dilute acid is 0.559 V. Arsenic(III) is stable in alkali and acid media and its oxidation by different oxidants has been investigated in acid media². Halides are important compounds and used in chemical reactions and in daily life. Inorganic and organic derivatives of radioactive ¹³¹I have been used in the treatment of certain thyroid and heart disorders. Silver halides are used in photography, as catalysts in industries etc.

Cerium is the most abundant of the rare earths. It is characterized chemically by varying two valance states, +3 cerious state (white) and +4 ceric states (orange red or yellowish). The ceric state is the only non-trivalent rare earth ion stable in high acid concentration. It is therefore strong oxidizer. Cerium(IV) is a well known oxidant in acid media^{3,4}, having the reduction potential¹ of the couple Ce^{IV}/Ce^{III} is 1.70 V.

The oxidation of organic compounds by cerium(IV), in general seems to proceed via the formation of an intermediate complex⁵. Among the inorganic substrates which serve as ligands for cerium(IV) are chloride, bromide and hypophosphite⁶. In sulphuric acid and sulphate media cerium(IV) forms several sulphate complexes^{3,4,7}, but their role has not received much attention so far. The redox potential of different couples involved in the reaction in acid media makes the iodide catalysis for the oxidation of arsenic(III) by cerium(IV) appear feasible. The slow cerium(IV) oxidation of arsenic(III) is facilitated by a minute (10^{-8} mol dm⁻³) quantity of iodide in aqueous sulphuric acid and sulphate media. The iodide catalyzed oxidation of arsenic(III) by cerium(IV) was studied earlier in acid medium^{8,9} but the study did not identified the active species of oxidant and reductant. The present investigation identified the active species of cerium(IV) and arsenic(III) and the mechanism of title reaction is discussed in terms of active species of oxidant and reductant and also compared with the bromide, chloride and iodide mediated⁹ oxidation of antimony by cerium(IV).

Results and discussion

Stoichiometry and product analysis :

Different sets of concentrations of reactants in 0.50 mol dm⁻³ sulphuric acid at constant ionic strength, *I* = 1.60 mol dm⁻³, were kept for over 4 h at room temperature in a closed container. When [cerium(IV)] > [arsenic(III)], the remaining cerium(IV) was assayed by measuring absorbance at 360 nm, where as under the conditions [arsenic(III)] > [cerium(IV)], when cerium(IV) had fully reacted, the remaining arsenic(III) concentration was determined by titrating with potassium iodate using starch as an indicator¹⁰. The product cerium(III) formed was oxidized to cerium(IV) with peroxodisulfate and its concentration was determined quantitatively by spectrophotometer at 360 nm. The results indicate that two moles of oxidant, cerium(IV), had reacted with one mole of arsenic(III) (Table 1) according to the following eq. (1).

The reaction orders were determined from the slopes of log *k*_{cat} versus log (concentration) plots by varying the concentration of cerium(IV), arsenic(III) sulphuric acid and catalyst, KI, while keeping all other concentrations and conditions constant.

Table 1. Stoichiometry^a of iodide mediated oxidation of arsenic(III) by cerium(IV) in aqueous sulphuric acid-sulfate media at 25 °C [H₂SO₄] = 0.50, *I* = 1.60 mol dm⁻³

[Ce ^{IV}] × 10 ⁴ (Taken)	[As ^{III}] × 10 ⁴ (Taken)	[Ce ^{IV}] × 10 ⁴ (Found)	[As ^{III}] × 10 ⁴ (Found)
1.0	1.0	-	0.52
1.0	2.0	-	1.48
2.0	1.0	-	-
5.0	1.0	3.02	-
5.0	2.0	1.03	-

^aAll concentrations are in mol dm⁻³.

At constant concentration of arsenic(III), 2.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ and at constant ionic strength, *I* = 1.60 mol dm⁻³, the cerium(IV) concentration was varied from 0.50 × 10⁻⁴ to 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ (Table 2). The order with respect to cerium(IV) concentration was found to be unity, since the rate constants *k*_{cat} were almost constant at different cerium(IV) concentrations (Table 2). The pseudo-first order plots under these conditions were straight line over 75% completion of the reaction also

Table 2. Effect of variation of cerium(IV) and arsenic(III) concentrations on the iodide mediated oxidation of arsenic(III) by cerium(IV) in aqueous sulphuric acid and sulphate medium at 25 °C and *I* = 1.60 mol dm⁻³

[Ce ^{IV}] × 10 ⁴ (mol dm ⁻³)	[As ^{III}] × 10 ² (mol dm ⁻³)	[H ₂ SO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)	[KI] × 10 ⁸ (mol dm ⁻³)	<i>k</i> _{cat} × 10 ³ (s ⁻¹)
0.50	2.0	0.5	5.0	1.80
1.0	2.0	0.5	5.0	1.88
2.0	2.0	0.5	5.0	1.75
3.0	2.0	0.5	5.0	1.78
4.0	2.0	0.5	5.0	1.90
5.0	2.0	0.5	5.0	1.86
1.0	1.0	0.5	5.0	1.40
1.0	2.0	0.5	5.0	1.88
1.0	4.0	0.5	5.0	2.40
1.0	6.0	0.5	5.0	2.92
1.0	8.0	0.5	5.0	3.30
1.0	10.0	0.5	5.0	3.65

indicates first order with respect to cerium(IV) concentration.

The substrate, arsenic(III) concentration was varied in the concentration range of 1.0 × 10⁻² to 1.0 × 10⁻¹ mol dm⁻³ at 25 °C, keeping all other conditions constant. The rate constant, *k*_{cat} increased with increase in the concentration of arsenic(III) (Table 2). From the slope of the plot of log *k*_{cat} versus log [As^{III}], the order with respect to arsenic(III) concentration was found to be less than unity (0.45).

At fixed ionic strength, *I* = 3.10 mol dm⁻³, and with other conditions remaining constant, the rate was found to increase with increasing acidity (Table 3). A constant amount of sulphuric acid, from the original cerium(IV) stock solution in all reaction mixture apart from the varying sulphuric acid, enables formation of various sulphato complexes of cerium(IV). The *in situ* H⁺ concentration in the reaction mixture was calculated using known ionization constant¹¹ of acid sulphate as in an earlier study^{12,13}. The order with respect to H⁺ ion concentration was fractional (0.50). Cerium(IV) is known to form several complexes in acid-sulphate media^{12,13} such as Ce(SO₄)²⁺, Ce(SO₄)₂, Ce(SO₄)₂HSO₄⁻ and H₃Ce(SO₄)₄⁻ as shown in equilibria (2)–(6).

The $\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}$ species may also be present, but its concentration may be very less and it can be neglected. Since the total cerium(IV) is distributed between different species with the equilibrium constant, $\beta_1 (=K_1) = 3.85 \times 10^2$, $\beta_2 (=K_1K_2) = 1.69 \times 10^2$, $\beta_3 (=K_1K_2K_3) = 1.01 \times 10^2$, $\beta_4 (=K_1K_2K_3K_4) = 2.03 \times 10^2$ and $K_{\text{OH}} = 15$. The approximate concentrations of cerium sulphate complexes can be calculated from the concentration of the dissolved cerium(IV), acid and sulphate by using the following eq. (7) and results are given in Table 3.

$$[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_t = [\text{Ce}^{4+}]_f \{1 + K_{\text{OH}}/[\text{H}^+] + \beta_1 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}] + \beta_2 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2 + \beta_3 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2 [\text{HSO}_4^-] + \beta_4 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2 [\text{HSO}_4^-]^2 [\text{H}^+]\} \quad (7)$$

In eq. (7) the subscripts 't' and 'f' stands for total and

$10^{-8} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (Table 4). As the catalyst concentration increases the rate of the reaction also increases, and activity of catalyst reaches a maximum after $[\text{I}^-] \geq 10.0 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ under the above mentioned experimental conditions. The order with respect to iodide concentration was found to be unity. Under the present experimental conditions the uncatalyzed reaction is immeasurably slow ($1.10 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$) and it has been neglected. Arsenic(III) is known to form different iodide complexes of general formula AsI_n^{+3-n} similar^{9,14} to that of antimony(III), 'n' being the number of iodide complexed and the respective equilibria are shown in (8) to (13).

Table 3. Variation of different cerium(IV) species^a with H^+ ion concentration on the iodide mediated oxidation of arsenic(III) by cerium(IV) in aqueous sulphuric acid medium at 25°C

$$[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4}, [\text{As}^{\text{III}}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2}, I = 3.10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$$

$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[\text{H}^+]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[\text{SO}_4^{2-}] \times 10^3$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$\alpha_0 \times 10^3$	$\alpha_{\text{OH}} \times 10^3$	$\alpha_1 \times 10$	$\alpha_2 \times 10^6$	$\alpha_3 \times 10^8$	$\alpha_4 \times 10^{10}$	$k_{\text{cat}} \times 10^3$ (s ⁻¹)
0.1	0.025	0.86	0.175	0.93	0.56	3.05	11.56	1.21	0.11	0.53
0.2	0.0593	0.693	0.341	1.62	0.41	4.30	13.14	2.67	1.09	0.78
0.3	0.1091	0.542	0.491	2.42	0.33	5.05	12.06	3.54	3.81	1.11
0.4	0.1804	0.414	0.620	3.53	0.29	5.62	10.24	3.79	8.50	1.39
0.5	0.2786	0.312	0.721	4.97	0.27	5.96	8.19	3.53	14.0	1.88
0.6	0.404	0.237	0.496	6.83	0.253	6.23	6.52	3.09	20.0	2.19
0.7	0.5519	0.185	0.848	9.01	0.245	6.42	5.24	2.65	25.0	2.44
0.8	0.7156	0.149	0.884	11.43	0.239	6.54	4.29	2.26	28.8	2.71
0.9	0.8899	0.123	0.910	13.99	0.235	6.63	3.59	1.95	31.8	3.22
1.0	1.0712	0.105	0.929	16.63	0.232	6.68	3.08	1.71	34.1	3.50

^a $\alpha_0, \alpha_{\text{OH}}, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$ and α_4 are the fractions of total Ce^{IV} of the species $\text{Ce}_f^{4+}, \text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}, \text{CeSO}_4^{2+}, \text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2, \text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2\text{HSO}_4^-$ and $\text{H}_3\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_4^-$ respectively.

free respectively. The formation of $[\text{Ce}(\text{OH})_2^{2+}]$ occurs to a much smaller extent and is therefore neglected. The results of such calculations were utilized to draw (Fig. 1), which shows that only $[\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)^{2+}]$ shows any parallel with the variation of rate with H^+ concentration. Hence it is assumed that $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)^{2+}$ is the active species of cerium(IV).

At constant oxidant, reductant and acid concentration of $1.0 \times 10^{-4}, 2.0 \times 10^{-2}$ and 0.50 mol dm^{-3} respectively, and $I = 1.60 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the catalyst, iodide concentration was varied between 1.0×10^{-8} and $10.0 \times$

As arsenic(III) behaves similar to that of antimony(III) in chloride media, the cumulative stability constants, $\beta_5 = 1.8 \times 10^2, \beta_6 = 3.1 \times 10^3, \beta_7 = 1.5 \times 10^4, \beta_8 = 5.3 \times 10^4, \beta_9 = 5.2 \times 10^4$ and $\beta_{10} = 1.3 \times 10^4$ of antimony(III)¹⁵ are taken to calculate the approximate concentrations of the arsenic(III) iodide complexes by using eq. (14) from the concentrations of the dissolved arsenic(III) and iodide with their competing equilibria¹⁶.

$$[\text{As}^{3+}]_t = [\text{As}^{3+}]_f \{1 + \beta_5 [\text{I}^-] + \beta_6 [\text{I}^-]^2 + \beta_7 [\text{I}^-]^3 + \beta_8 [\text{I}^-]^4 + \beta_9 [\text{I}^-]^5 + \beta_{10} [\text{I}^-]^6\} \quad (14)$$

Fig. 1. Effect of acid concentration on different cerium(IV) species and also on the rate constant (α_2 and α_3 values decreases as the H^+ ion concentration increases and hence not shown in the graph).

Table 4. Effect of variation of iodide ion concentration on arsenic(III) species^a and on the rate constants of oxidation of arsenic(III) by cerium(IV) in aqueous sulphuric acid and sulphate media at 25 °C
 $[Ce^{IV}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$, $[As^{III}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2}$, $[H_2SO_4] = 0.50$, $I = 1.60 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

$[I^-] \times 10^8$ (mol dm ⁻³)	α_5	$\alpha_6 \times 10^5$	$\alpha_7 \times 10^{12}$	$\alpha_8 \times 10^{18}$	$\alpha_9 \times 10^{26}$	$\alpha_{10} \times 10^{34}$	$\alpha_{11} \times 10^{42}$	$k_{cat} \times 10^3$ (s ⁻¹)
0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.11
1	0.99	0.18	0.31	0.015	0.053	0.052	0.013	0.36
2	0.99	0.36	1.24	0.120	0.848	1.66	0.832	0.74
3	0.99	0.54	2.79	0.405	4.29	12.63	9.48	1.12
4	0.99	0.72	4.96	0.960	13.6	53.2	53.3	1.51
5	0.99	0.90	7.75	1.88	32.5	168.0	203.0	1.88
6	0.99	1.08	11.2	3.24	68.7	404	606	2.29
7	0.99	1.26	15.2	5.14	127	874	1529	2.63
8	0.99	1.44	19.8	7.68	217	1703	3408	2.95
9	0.99	1.62	25.1	10.9	347	3070	6908	3.38
10	0.99	1.80	31.0	15.0	530	5200	1300	3.32

^a $\alpha_5, \alpha_6, \alpha_7, \alpha_8, \alpha_9, \alpha_{10}$ and α_{11} are the fractions of total arsenic(III) of the species $As_5^{3+}, AsI^{2+}, AsI_2^+, AsI_3, AsI_4^-, AsI_5^{2-}$ and AsI_6^{3-} respectively.

In eq. (14) the subscripts 't' and 'f' stand for total and free respectively.

Variation in the concentrations of such species with increase in iodide concentration is shown in Table 4 together with the rate of reaction. These results are utilized to draw Fig. 2 and a parallel is found only between rate constant, k_{cat} and AsI^{2+} species concentrations. Hence AsI^{2+} species is considered as the active species of arsenic(III).

At constant concentration of reactants and other con-

ditions constant, the ionic strength was varied between 1.60 to 3.20 mol dm⁻³ by varying the concentrations of sodium sulphate and found that the ionic strength did not has any significant effect on the rate of reaction. The effect of dielectric constant was studied by varying the mixtures of acetic acid-water (v/v). It was found that the rate constant increased with decreasing dielectric constant of the medium. No reaction of the solvent with the oxidant is occurred under the experimental conditions employed. A plot of $\log k_{cat}$ versus $1/D$ is linear with positive slope.

Fig. 2. Effect of I^- ion concentration on arsenic(III) species and on the rate constant of the iodide mediated oxidation of arsenic(III) by cerium(IV) in aqueous sulphuric acid medium at 25 °C.

The effect of initially added product, cerium(III) and arsenic(V) were studied in the 0.50×10^{-4} to 5.0×10^{-4} mol dm $^{-3}$ concentration range, keeping the ionic strength, reactant concentrations and other conditions constant. It was found that cerium(III) and arsenic(V) did not have any significant effect on the rate of reaction.

The rate of reaction was measured at 25, 30, 35 and 40 °C. The rate was found to increase with increasing temperature (Table 5). The energy of activation E_a , was calculated from the slope of the Arrhenius plot, $\log k_{cat}$ versus $1/T$. The enthalpy of activation, ΔH^\ddagger and the entropy of activation, ΔS^\ddagger , were obtained by the Eyring equation.

$$k = k_B T/h e^{(-\Delta G^\ddagger/RT)}$$

$$= k_B T/h e^{-(\Delta H^\ddagger + T\Delta S^\ddagger)/RT} \quad (15)$$

k is the rate constant, k_B is the Boltzmann's constant, R is the gas constant, T is the absolute temperature and ΔG^\ddagger is the free energy of activation. The linear form of above eq. (15) is

$$\ln k/T = -\Delta H^\ddagger/RT + \Delta S^\ddagger/R + \ln k_B/h \quad (16)$$

The slope of the plot of $\log k/T$ versus $1/T$ gives the value of enthalpy of activation. By using the value ΔH^\ddagger and the rate constant at a particular temperature T , the value of ΔS^\ddagger was obtained by simple rearrangement of eq. (15). Using these values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger , the obtained free

energy of activation, ΔG^\ddagger_{298} is 89 ± 3 kJ mol $^{-1}$. The values are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5

(a) Effect of temperature on the iodide mediated oxidation of arsenic(III) by cerium(IV) in aqueous sulphuric acid-sulphate media ($I = 5.0 \times 10^{-8}$ mol dm $^{-3}$)

Temp. (K)	$k_{cat} \times 10^3$ (s $^{-1}$)	Activation parameters	Values
298	1.88	E_a (kJ mol $^{-1}$)	44 ± 1
303	2.56	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol $^{-1}$)	42 ± 3
308	3.45	ΔS^\ddagger (J K $^{-1}$ mol $^{-1}$)	-158 ± 5
313	4.39	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol $^{-1}$)	89 ± 3

(b) Effect of temperature on the bromide, chloride and iodide mediated oxidation of antimony(III) by cerium(IV) in aqueous sulphuric acid-sulfate media (Ref. no. 9)

Temp. (K)	$[Br^-] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3}$ (mol dm $^{-3}$)	$[Cl^-] = 5.0 \times 10^{-2}$ (mol dm $^{-3}$)	$[I^-] = 5.0 \times 10^{-7}$ (mol dm $^{-3}$)
	$k_{cat} \times 10^3$ (s $^{-1}$)	$k_{cat} \times 10^3$ (s $^{-1}$)	$k_{cat} \times 10^3$ (s $^{-1}$)
293	3.72	2.56	4.49
298	4.47	3.02	6.22
303	7.11	5.12	9.66
308	9.45	7.30	12.3

Activation parameters :

E_a (kJ mol $^{-1}$)	51 ± 2	54 ± 2	53 ± 3
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol $^{-1}$)	48 ± 2	51 ± 2	51 ± 2
ΔS^\ddagger (J K $^{-1}$ mol $^{-1}$)	-129 ± 4	-120 ± 4	-116 ± 4
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol $^{-1}$)	86 ± 4	87 ± 3	86 ± 3

It has been pointed out by Moelwyn-Hughes¹⁷ that in presence of the catalyst, the uncatalyzed and catalyzed reactions proceed simultaneously, so that,

$$k_{\text{cat}} = k_u + K_C [\text{Catalyst}]^x$$

where k_{cat} is the observed pseudo-first order rate constant in the presence of catalyst; k_u is the pseudo-first order rate constant in the absence of the catalyst, K_C is the catalytic constant and 'x' is the order with respect to catalyst. Then the value of K_C is calculated by using the following equation

$$K_C = \frac{k_t - k_u}{[\text{Catalyst}]^x} = \frac{k_c}{[\text{Catalyst}]}$$

where $k_t - k_u = k_c$

In the present study the values of 'x' is 1.0. The catalytic constant is found to be 35.4×10^3 at 25 °C.

The oxidation of antimony(III) by cerium(IV) in presence of bromide, chloride and iodide in sulphuric acid-sulfate media has been studied earlier⁹. The cerium(IV) oxidation of arsenic(III) is slow in aqueous sulphuric and sulphate media. However, the reaction occurs with reasonable rates in the presence of minute quantity (10^{-8} mol dm⁻³) of iodide ions in aqueous sulphuric acid and sulphate media. The stoichiometry of the iodide mediated oxidation of arsenic(III) is similar to that of bromide, chloride and iodide mediated oxidation of antimony(III) by cerium(IV), i.e. 1 : 2 (reductant : oxidant). In the bromide, chloride and iodide mediated oxidation of antimony(III) by cerium(IV), the order with respect to oxidant and reductant concentrations were found to be unity and less than unity, respectively. The similar results were obtained in the iodide mediated oxidation of arsenic(III) by cerium(IV) in sulphuric acid and sulphate media. In both the cases, iodide mediated oxidation of arsenic(III) by cerium(IV) and bromide, chloride and iodide mediated oxidation of antimony(III) by cerium(IV), as the sulphuric acid concentration increases in the reaction mixture, the H⁺ ion concentration increased, the rate of reaction also increased and in both cases the order with respect to acid concentration was found to be less than unity. The fractional order with respect to H⁺ ion concentration might be arisen due to its role being involved in the formation of several cerium(IV) complexes in acid-sulfate media. As discussed in the preceding sec-

tion, cerium(IV) forms several complexes in sulphuric acid and sulphate media^{3,9}. In the bromide, chloride and iodide mediated oxidation of antimony(III) by cerium(IV), the active species of oxidant was found to be $\text{H}_3\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_4^-$, whereas, in the iodide mediated oxidation of arsenic(III) by cerium(IV), the active species of oxidant is $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2+}$ (Fig. 1). In both cases, as the catalysts concentration is increased, the rate of reaction also increased. The order with respect to catalysts concentration is unity in both the cases. In the presence of bromide, chloride and iodide, antimony(III) forms different antimony bromide, antimony chloride and antimony iodide complexes respectively. It has been found that, SbBr_2^+ , SbCl_3 and SbI^{2+} are the active species of bromide, chloride and iodide respectively in the bromide, chloride and iodide mediated oxidation of antimony(III) by cerium(IV) in sulphuric acid and sulfate media. Similarly, in the presence of iodide, arsenic(III) forms different iodide complexes. In the present study, from Fig. 2, it is clear that, the concentration of AsI^{2+} species almost parallels the rate, which indicates that the active species of arsenic(III) is AsI^{2+} .

In the iodide mediated oxidation of arsenic(III) by cerium(IV), initially added products did not have any significant effect on the rate of reaction. Similar results were also obtained in the bromide, chloride and iodide mediated oxidation of antimony(III) by cerium(IV). From all these experimental results, the mechanism for the iodide mediated oxidation of arsenic(III) by cerium(IV) is given in the following Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

In the Scheme 1 arsenic(III) reacts with I⁻ ion to form AsI^{2+} species and cerium(IV) in presence of sulphuric acid-sulfate media forms $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2+}$ species in the prior equilibrium steps. Thus, formed active species, AsI^{2+}

and $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2+}$ react together to give an intermediate arsenic(IV), a product cerium(III), with generation of the catalyst in a rate determining step. Then in a further fast step, the intermediate arsenic(IV) reacts with another mole of $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2+}$ to give the final products, arsenic(V) and cerium(III).

Similar to the oxidation of antimony(III) by cerium(IV), the oxidation of arsenic(III) by cerium(IV) is also a non-complementary reaction, and may occur by the intervention of reactive arsenic(IV) or antimony(IV) species. The formation of intermediate, arsenic(IV) is also in accordance with earlier work¹². No experimental evidence for the formation of arsenic(IV) or antimony(IV) is available, but the experimental data rule out a single two equivalent step.

From Scheme 1 the rate law (22) can be derived as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= \frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = k[\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2+}][\text{AsI}^{2+}] \\ &= k \beta_1 \beta_6 [\text{Ce}^{4+}][\text{As}^{3+}][\text{SO}_4^{2-}][\text{I}^-] \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

The total concentration of cerium(IV) is given by

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{Ce}^{4+}]_t &= [\text{Ce}^{4+}]_f + [\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2+}] \\ &= [\text{Ce}^{4+}]_f + \beta_1 [\text{Ce}^{4+}][\text{SO}_4^{2-}] \\ &= [\text{Ce}^{4+}]_f \{1 + \beta_1 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$[\text{Ce}^{4+}]_f = \frac{[\text{Ce}^{4+}]_t}{(1 + \beta_1 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}])} \quad (18)$$

where subscripts 't' and 'f' stands for total and free respectively.

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{As}^{3+}]_t &= [\text{As}^{3+}]_f + \text{AsI}^{2+} \\ &= [\text{As}^{3+}]_f + \beta_6 [\text{AsI}^{3+}][\text{I}^-] \\ &= [\text{As}^{3+}]_f \{1 + \beta_6 [\text{I}^-]\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$[\text{As}^{3+}]_f = \frac{[\text{As}^{3+}]_t}{(1 + \beta_6 [\text{I}^-])} \quad (18)$$

In the experiment a very low concentration of iodide is used, hence the term $(1 + \beta_6 [\text{I}^-])$ can be neglected in the denominator of eq. (19).

So,

$$[\text{As}^{3+}]_f = [\text{As}^{3+}]_t \quad (20)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{I}^-]_t &= [\text{I}^-]_f + \text{AsI}^{2+} \\ &= [\text{I}^-]_f + \beta_6 [\text{As}^{3+}][\text{I}^-] \\ &= [\text{I}^-]_f \{1 + \beta_6 [\text{As}^{3+}]\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$[\text{I}^-]_f = \frac{[\text{I}^-]_t}{(1 + \beta_6 [\text{As}^{3+}])} \quad (21)$$

Substituting eqs. (18), (20) and (21) in the eq. (17) and omitting the subscripts we have,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= \frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = \frac{k \beta_1 \beta_6 [\text{Ce}^{4+}][\text{As}^{3+}][\text{SO}_4^{2-}][\text{I}^-]}{(1 + \beta_1 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}])(1 + \beta_6 [\text{As}^{3+}])} \\ &= \frac{k \beta_1 \beta_6 [\text{Ce}^{4+}][\text{As}^{3+}][\text{SO}_4^{2-}][\text{I}^-]}{(1 + \beta_6 [\text{As}^{3+}]) + \beta_1 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}] + \beta_1 \beta_6 [\text{As}^{3+}][\text{SO}_4^{2-}]} \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

or

$$\frac{\text{Rate}}{[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]} = k_{\text{cat}} = \frac{k \beta_1 \beta_6 [\text{Ce}^{4+}][\text{As}^{3+}][\text{SO}_4^{2-}][\text{I}^-]}{1 + \beta_6 [\text{As}^{3+}] + \beta_1 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}] + \beta_1 \beta_6 [\text{As}^{3+}][\text{SO}_4^{2-}]} \quad (22)$$

The rate eq. (22) may be rearranged to eq. (23) which is suitable for verification.

$$\frac{[\text{I}^-]}{k_{\text{cat}}} = \frac{1}{k \beta_1 \beta_6 [\text{As}^{3+}][\text{SO}_4^{2-}]} + \frac{1}{k \beta_1 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]} + \frac{1}{k \beta_6 [\text{As}^{3+}]} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (23)$$

According to eq. (23), the plots of $[\text{I}^-]/k_{\text{cat}}$ versus $1/[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ and $[\text{I}^-]/k_{\text{cat}}$ versus $1/[\text{As}^{3+}]$ should be linear and are found to be so (Fig. 3).

(I) From the first plot, i.e. $[\text{I}^-]/k_{\text{cat}}$ versus $1/[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$:

$$(\text{Slope})_1 = \frac{(1 + \beta_6 [\text{As}^{3+}])}{k \beta_1 \beta_6 [\text{As}^{3+}]} \quad (24)$$

Fig. 3. Verification of rate law (22) in the form of (23).

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\text{Intercept})_1 &= \frac{1}{k \beta_6 [\text{As}^{3+}]} + \frac{1}{k} \\
 &= \frac{(1 + \beta_6 [\text{As}^{3+}])}{k \beta_6 [\text{As}^{3+}]} \quad (25)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{(\text{Intercept})_1}{(\text{Slope})_1} &= \frac{0.25 \times 10^{-5}}{1.233 \times 10^{-5}} = \beta_1 = 0.1622 \\
 &= \text{Formation constant of } \text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2^{2+} \quad (26)
 \end{aligned}$$

(II) From the second plot, i.e. $[\text{I}^-]/k_{\text{cat}}$ versus $1/[\text{As}^{3+}]$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\text{Intercept})_2 &= \frac{1}{k \beta_6 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]} + \frac{1}{k} \\
 (\text{Slope})_2 &= \frac{(1 + \beta_1 + [\text{SO}_4^{2-}])}{k \beta_1 \beta_6 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]} \quad (27)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{1 + \beta_1 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]}{k \beta_1 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]} \quad (28)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{(\text{Intercept})_2}{(\text{Slope})_2} &= \frac{2.1 \times 10^{-5}}{1.24 \times 10^{-6}} = \beta_6 = 16.94 \\
 &= \text{Formation constant of } \text{AsI}^{2+} \quad (29)
 \end{aligned}$$

Substituting the values of β_1 and $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ in the (Intercept)₂ of the second plot, i.e. in the eq. (28), one obtains the value of k , the rate constant with respect to slow step of Scheme 1. By this procedure the obtained values of k , β_1 and β_6 are $6.347 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $0.1622 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and $16.94 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. The effect of ionic strength is difficult to interpret in view of the various ions involved in the reaction media and high ionic strength used. The increase in the acetic acid content in the reaction medium leads to an increase in the rate of reaction, which supports the reaction between two positively charged ions (Scheme 1).

The iodide mediated oxidation of arsenic(III) by cerium(IV) in aqueous sulphuric acid-sulfate media and bromide, chloride and iodide mediated oxidation of antimony(III) by cerium(IV) in aqueous sulphuric acid and sulfate media were studied at four different temperatures. The results are given in Table 5. The catalysts modify the reaction path by lowering the energy of activation. In both cases the negative value of ΔS^\ddagger indicates, the activated complex is more ordered than the reactants.

A bridge is proposed for Br^- mediated cerium(IV)-antimony(III) reaction. The importance of bridging anions in facilitating electron transfer in inorganic reactions

is well known. A chloride ion bridge accelerated mechanism has been found in many exchange reactions¹⁸ including Ce^{IV}-Ce^{III} exchange. In all such cases, there are two possibilities for the mechanism. The electron may first be transferred and anion may then move in the opposite direction; alternatively, chloride atom transfer may take place. Whatever the mechanism, the oxidation-reduction probably takes place through the formation of bridge. Taube and coworkers¹⁹ have demonstrated the transfer of large number of univalent atoms and groups. Apart from the bridge theory, the great tendency of chloride ion to complex with the reaction product Sb^V makes conditions more favorable²⁰ for the reaction. Similar things might also happen in presence of bromide as catalyst. The present reaction is slow in the absence of bromide ion in 1 mol dm⁻³ sulphuric acid, whereas in the presence of bromide ion, the electron transfer might take place through sulphate bridge²¹, which is known to be not very effective. This group is also not transferred, because Sb^V has no tendency to co-ordinate with SO₄²⁻ and the rate is slow. In the absence of bromide ion, Sb^{III} in sulphuric acid is known to exist as SbO⁺. Coulombic repulsion between various ions present in solution and SbO⁺ might be another important factor leading to a slower rate in the absence of bromide ion. The activation parameters evaluated for the presence and absence of halides explain the catalytic effect on the reaction. The catalyst, iodide modifies the reaction path by lowering the energy of activation.

Comparison of oxidation capacities of antimony(III) and arsenic(III) :

Although antimony(III) and arsenic (III) belongs to the same group having similar properties but, we have observed different oxidation capacities. Antimony(III) and arsenic(III) are also having the more or less same reduction potential (Sb^V/Sb^{III} : 0.581 V; As^V/As^{III} : 0.559 V) in acid media. Antimony forms two series of halides SbX₃ and SbX₅ and authors assumed that arsenic also forms similar types of halides. The oxidation of antimony(III) by cerium(IV) in acid medium is catalyzed by iodide, bromide and chloride. Similarly, the oxidation of arsenic(III) by cerium(IV) is also catalyzed by iodide, bromide and chloride in acid medium. Based on our kinetic results, in the case of iodide, bromide and chloride mediated oxidation of antimony(III) by cerium(IV), the rate

constants are less than the iodide mediated oxidation of arsenic(III) by cerium(IV). This is because arsenic(III) is more electronegative than antimony(III). The energy of activation and entropy of activation in case of iodide mediated oxidation of arsenic(III) by cerium(IV) are lower than that of iodide, bromide and chloride mediated oxidation of antimony(III) by cerium(IV). The free energy of activation in the former case is larger than the latter case. These experimental results indicate that, arsenic(III) has got more oxidizing capacity than antimony(III) in acid medium.

Comparison of catalytic effect :

The values of catalytic constant K_C (dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹) for iodide mediated oxidation of arsenic(III) by cerium(IV) (present work), as well as bromide, chloride and iodide mediated⁹ oxidation of antimony(III) by cerium(IV) at 25 °C are calculated. The results indicate that catalytic activity increases in the order of I⁻ > Br⁻ > Cl⁻ and I⁻ is more efficient catalyst than Br⁻ and Cl⁻. According to bridge theory the electron transfer or effectiveness of bridge decreases in the order of I⁻ > Br⁻ > Cl⁻. The difference in the most polarizable ligand must transfer most easily. This type of behaviour is already known²².

Conclusion :

The reaction between cerium(IV) and arsenic(III) is very slow in sulphuric acid medium at 25 °C. However, the reaction is facile in presence of micro (10⁻⁸ mol dm⁻³) amounts of iodide in aqueous sulphuric acid medium. The active species of oxidant and substrate are identified as Ce(SO₄)²⁺ and AsI²⁺ respectively. The results indicate that catalytic activity increases in the order of I⁻ > Br⁻ > Cl⁻.

Experimental

Reagent grade chemicals were used. Double distilled water was used throughout. The stock solution of the oxidant, cerium(IV) (0.010 mol dm⁻³) was obtained by dissolving cerium(IV) ammonium sulphate (E. Merck) in 1.0 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄. The solution was standardized by titrating against iron(II) ammonium sulphate solution using ferroin as an indicator¹⁰. The arsenic(III) stock solution was made by dissolving arsenic(III) oxide (BDH, AR) in 1.0 mol dm⁻³ sodium hydroxide. The stock solution of arsenic(III) was neutralized with 1.0 mol dm⁻³ sulphuric acid before standardization. The solution was standar-

dized¹⁰ with potassium iodate using starch as an indicator, till the colorless solution changes to blue. The stock solution of 0.01 mol dm⁻³ KI solution was prepared by dissolving KI (Glaxo, AR) in double distilled water. The stock solutions were diluted as required before use. Cerium(III) solution was prepared by dissolving cerium(III) sulphate (CDH) in water. Sodium sulphate and sulphuric acid were used to provide ionic strength and acidity respectively.

All kinetic measurements were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions where arsenic(III) concentration was excess over cerium(IV) concentration at a constant ionic strength of 1.60 mol dm⁻³. But in case of variation of acid concentration the ionic strength was kept at 3.10 mol dm⁻³. The reaction was initiated by mixing thermally equilibrated (25 ± 0.1 °C) solutions of cerium(IV) and arsenic(III) which also containing the required quantities of sulphuric acid, sodium sulphate and potassium iodide catalyst were mixed. The reaction was followed by monitoring the decrease in absorbance of cerium(IV) in the reaction mixture at 360 nm in a 1 cm cell placed in a thermostatted compartment of a Varian Cary 50 Bio UV-Visible spectrophotometer as a function of time. The application of Beer's law under the reaction condition had been verified in the concentration range 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ to 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ of cerium(IV) at 360 nm and the extinction coefficient was found to be $\epsilon = 3500 \pm 50 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The kinetics were followed more than 80% completion of the reaction and good first order kinetics were observed. The pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{cat} were calculated from the slopes of the plots of $\log a/(a-x)$ versus time. The pseudo-first order plots were linear over 75% completion of the reaction. The k_{cat} values were reproducible within ±5% and are the average of at least three independent kinetic runs.

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